

The Buddha of the Śrī Mahā Bodhi Shrine at the Mahāvihāra in Anurādhapura

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Plate 1. The Bodhi-tree at Anurādhapura.
Tennent, J. E. 1859. *Ceylon*, Vol I, p. 343.

While working on my compendium *Buddhist Sculptures in Sri Lanka* during the 1980s, I discovered in the archives of the Archaeological Department of Sri Lanka in Colombo a photograph taken in 1895 by Captain J. R. Hogg (1870-1939) at an unrecorded location in Sri Lanka. It depicts an ancient seated stone Buddha image half buried in the ground (**Plate 2**). At this moment I also realized that the photograph depicts the only Sri Lankan Buddha displaying the gesture of touching the earth (*bhūmisparśa-mudrā*). This is indicated by the right arm pointing forward, something not visible if the earth would have been just one inch higher. There wasn't any label indicating the location where the photograph was taken, nor did I have any idea about the size of the Buddha image. Therefore, the only possibility to get some idea about the dimensions of the Buddha, was to get an identification of the plants beside the image. During a later visit to the botanical garden in Kandy I was able to get information about the kind of plant and the approximate size of their leaves. I was then able to estimate that the Buddha image must be taller than 3 metres, thus surpassing in height all seated Sri Lankan stone Buddhas carved in one piece known to me. Assuming that such a large image could actually only be located at Anurādhapura, I concentrated my search to the monuments of the ancient capital. The crucial indication for finding the image was the size and the fact that the right arm pointed forward instead with both hands placed in the lap as usual with most other Sri Lanka Buddhas. After showing the ancient photograph of the Buddha to several older guards protecting the archaeological monuments of Anurādhapura I was directed to the image-house east of the Śrī Mahā Bodhi Shrine at the Mahāvihāra complex. However, my excitement was replaced with disappointment once I realized that the tall seated Buddha looking new in every aspect was actually the image photographed by Captain J. R. Hogg in 1895. This Buddha had been unprotected for many centuries with the soil around slowly raising due to decomposing leaves and left-overs by the officiating priests and endless procession of worshippers. For the purpose of the reconstruction of the present image-house in 1911 at the location of the half-buried dolomite Buddha, the image was excavated and had to be lifted to a higher ground. Due to the importance of this image regarding the worship of the Bodhi-tree, the priests in charge had it covered with plaster and painted according to the style then prevalent (**Plate 5**). Nowadays, hidden behind glass panels, few if any of the visitors have an idea that this image dates back to *circa* the 6th century. Whereas the common Buddhist worshippers are ignorant regarding the actual date and outer appearance, the removal of the plaster to reveal the original Buddha would dramatically enhance the emotional experience of all viewers.

Plate 2. Buddha Śākyamuni. Dolomite marble. Height: 3.3 meters. Late Anurādhapura Period, *circa* 6th century. Śrī Mahā Bodhi Shrine at the Mahāvihāra complex at Anurādhapura. (Photo: Captain J. R. Hogg, 1895).

The largest – and also in other aspects the most spectacular – stone image of a seated Buddha in Sri Lanka is located since about the sixth century on the premises of the Śrī Mahā Bodhi Shrine at the Mahāvihāra complex at Anurādhapura. The statue is carved out of a single slab of dolomite marble, measures 3.3 metres in height and is since 1911 installed in the image-house located east of the sacred Bodhi-tree. This Buddha is presumably the only known Sri Lankan Buddha seated in the “diamond posture” (*vajraparyāṅkāsa*) with both soles pointing upwards, and displaying the gesture of touching the earth (*bhūmisparśa-mudrā* or *māravijaya-mudrā*). All other seated Sri Lankan Buddhas usually rest in the “noble posture” (*sattvaparyāṅkāsa*) with the right leg placed upon the left leg with only the sole of the right foot visible, displaying instead the gesture of meditation with both hands placed in the lap (*dhyāna-mudrā*). The gesture of touching the earth (*bhūmisparśa-mudrā*) symbolizes Buddha Siddhartha’s defeat of Māra (*māravijaya*) and subsequent enlightenment under the Bodhi-tree at Bodhgayā (Gayā district, Bihar, N.-E. India). The only known Sri Lankan Buddha image displaying the *bhūmisparśa-mudrā* is thus fittingly placed beside the principal Bodhi-tree of Sri Lanka located at the Mahāvihāra complex. This Buddha was commissioned to be installed in the Śrī Mahā Bodhi Shrine and likely copied after an early North-Eastern Indian Pāla style image (**Plate 3**). The hollow carved eyes of the image were originally inset with crystal and precious stones, something conferred only for very important Buddha images (**Plate 4**).¹ According to the Vēlāikkāras inscription slab discovered near the Aṭadāgē at Polonnaruva, the eyes made of crystal and precious stones were once every year temporarily removed during the anointment ceremony: “*It became also the auspicious house for the first anointment ceremony and the Hall of Fragrance for the auspicious and colossal stone statue of the holy Buddha, in which is held annually the ceremony of unloosening the sacred eyes and applying collyrium to them*”.² It can be assumed that the Bodhi-tree Buddha had also yearly anointment ceremonies until the defeat of the Sinhalese at the hand of the powerful Colas

Plate 3. Buddha Śākyamuni displaying the *bhūmisparśa-mudrā*. Early Pāla Style, circa 6th century. Black stone. Height: 81 cm. Museum, Kolkata)

Plate 4. Eyes of some image were originally inset with crystal and precious stones. ASCPR, *Ninth* (Indian *Ninth Progress Report 1892*, pl. VI

1 Such remains of eyes assembled of two pieces of crystal enclosing a precious stone pupil were excavated – among other locations – at the Abhayagiri monastic ruins at Anurādhapura [ASCPR, *Ninth Progress Report 1892*, pl. VI] and at Pankuliya of the Aśokārāma Vihāra ruins at Anurādhapura [ASCPR, *Seventh Progress Report 1891*, pl. XVIII].

2 Wickremasinghe, D. M. de Z. *Epigraphia Zeylanica*, Vol. II: 254.

(983–1014 AD) of the South Indias. As a result the Buddhist monasteries of Anurādhapura and elsewhere suffered from want of any official patronage and gradually became deserted and overgrown. As recorded in the *Mahāvamsa* (Great Chronicle) in about the third century BC King Aśoka’s son Mahinda arrived in Sri Lanka and transmitted the teachings of Buddha to King Devānampiyatissa (ruled c. 250–210 BC). Mahinda recommended to the ruler of Sri Lanka to send an envoy to Bodhgayā to obtain the south branch of the Bodhi-tree under which the historical Buddha Siddharta had attained enlightenment. King Aśoka’s daughter Saṅghamittā is credited to have brought the branch to Sri Lanka. The tree, according to Sinhalese tradition, was planted by Devānampiyatissa inside a square courtyard of the Mahāvihāra complex enclosed by a retaining wall (*prākāra*) with four entrances. The Bodhi-tree temple was built by Vasabha (c. 67–111 AD) and allegedly contained four [Buddha] images. Vohārikatissa (c. 209–231 AD) is credited with the installation of two bronze [Buddha] images on the east side of the Bodhi-tree temple. Among the additions and restorations done by Goṭhābhaya (c. 249-262 AD) were the placement of a stone throne (*āsanaghara*) at the south entrance, while at the west, north and east entrances three stone Buddhas were installed. Mahāsenā (c. 274–301 AD) added two bronze [Buddha] images on the west side of the same image-house. Dhātusena (c. 455-473 AD) is credited with the setting up of sixteen “bath-maidens” cast in bronze. Dhātusena (c. 455–473 AD) built a Bodhisattva shrine. This temple was later rebuilt by Aggabodhi (c. 772–777 AD). It was restored and gilded by Dapulla II (c. 815–831 AD), who also enshrined a golden Buddha image. The Bodhi-tree house constructed by Devānampiyatissa was re-roofed by Mahānāga (c. 569-571 AD) who also installed images.³ An inscription executed in the first regnal year of king Siri Sang-bo Abha [Mahinda IV (956–972 AD)?] mentions the stone Buddha inside the Bodhi-tree House.⁴ It is also recorded that Vijayabāhu I (c. 1055–1110 AD) undertook some repairs.⁵

Plate 5. Buddha Śākyamuni. Dolomite marble, covered in 1911 with plaster and paint. Height: 3.3 meters. Late Anurādhapura Period, circa 6th century. Śrī Mahā Bodhi Shrine at the Mahāvihāra complex at Anurādhapura. (Photo: 2020).

- ³ Nicholas, C. W. 1959. “Historical Topography of Ancient and Medieval Ceylon”, *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society (Ceylon Branch) New Series*, Vol. 6: 130–131.
- ⁴ Wickremasinghe, D. M. de Z. *Epigraphia Zeylanica*, Vol. II: 69–70.
- ⁵ Nicholas, C. W. 1959. “Historical Topography of Ancient and Medieval Ceylon”, *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society (Ceylon Branch) New Series*, Vol. 6: 131–132, 147.

Faxian, the Chinese pilgrim, left the following account of his visit to the Śrī Mahā Bodhi Shrine during his stay in Sri Lanka in the years 411 to 413 AD, which was during the reign of King Mahānāma (c. 406–428 AD): “*At the foot of the tree a shrine has been built, with the image of Buddha seated inside, an object of ceaseless worship to priests and laymen*”.⁶ The image seen by Faxian in the early 5th century cannot be the one installed at present in the Śrī Mahā Bodhi Shrine at the Mahāvihāra complex, dating earliest from the 6th century. Therefore it can be concluded that the present Buddha image was likely not the first one to be installed near the Bodhi tree, but possibly the first depicted with the gesture of touching the earth (*bhūmisparśa-mudrā*). The Buddha inside the Bodhi-tree House is stylistically very similar to the famous Samādhi image located at the nearby Bodhigara site of the Abhayagiri Vihara complex (**Plate 6**).

Plate 6. Samādhi Buddha with hollow carved eyes. Dolomite marble. Height: 1.98 meters. Late Anurādhapura Period, *circa* 6th century. Bodhigara site. Abhayagiri Vihāra, Anurādhapura. (Photo: Scowen & Co. 1870–1890).

Literature

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⁶ Giles, H. A. 1923. *The Travels of Fa-Hsien [399–414 AD]*: 68.

Plate 7. Śrī Mahā Bodhi Shrine west entrance. (Photo: Joseph Lawton. 1870–1871).

Plate 8. Śrī Mahā Bodhi Shrine. (Photo: Dr. Martin Hürlimann, 1929).